

A Brief Review Article on Caper Berries

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Abstract

One of the most popular medicinal plants, *Capparispinosa* L., is widely used throughout the world to treat a variety of human ailments. With reference to *C. spinosa*'s traditional usage, growing methods, and phytochemical components, this research attempts to critically analyze the pertinent scientific literature. Iranian diabetes patients customarily consume the fruit of the caper plant, *Capparis spinosa* L. No controlled human investigation has yet been done to evaluate its effectiveness in treating hyperglycemia in type 2 diabetic patients. The caper, or *Capparispinosa* L., is an aromatic plant that grows in the majority of the Mediterranean basin and certain areas of western Asia. *C. spinosa* L. has been used in traditional phytomedicine for a very long time as a medicinal herb. Extracted from *C. spinosa* L. are polyphenols and many bioactive compounds. reveal a variety of medicinal qualities that have drawn attention to this plant as a potential health booster.

Keywords: caper berries, Alkaloids, Flavonoids, Type 2 Diabetic, Antioxidant Activity

Introduction

Caper is a shrubby plant that is indigenous to the Mediterranean region (*Capparis spinosa* L.). It is a member of the genus *Capparis* and the family *Capparidaceae*, which together contain over 250 species used mostly for decorative, culinary, cosmetic, pharmacological, and therapeutic applications [1]. High morphological and ecological variety in *Capparis spinosa* has prompted some authors to distinguish a number of intraspecific variations and species [2-5]. It is well adaptable to hot temperatures, bright sunlight, and changing climates, and it plays significant socioeconomic roles in many countries' dry regions [6-8].

A shrub with high therapeutic value is the caper. This species is abundant in bioactive

substances that can be employed for therapeutic, culinary, and ornamental purposes, including flavonoids, glucosinolates, phenolic acids, and alkaloids. Along this line, numerous health-promoting qualities of caper extracts, including antioxidant and anti-cancer activities, were scientifically proven [9]. Since it aids in retaining biodiversity, soil water, and prevents soil erosion, capers are also utilized for ecological purposes [10, 11].

The caper, also known as *Capparis spinosa* L., is one of the unusual shrub plants that offer a wide range of useful properties [12]. It is an unusually limitless, xerophytic, and heliophilous plant that grows in the Mediterranean region [13, 14]. It must tolerate

the harsh weather conditions in dry and semi-arid regions with high temperatures. In this way, it can serve a very important biological role in these locations to prevent soil erosion, but it can also be grown for other purposes.

The *C. spinosa* L. plant resembles a bush with long, flexible, and drooping branches that all emerge from a single, enormous strain. It is a thorny shrub with a wooden trunk. It is typically between 1 and 1.5 meters wide and 0.40 to 0.80 meters high^[15]. The spiny leaf stipules of *C. spinosa* L. represent the *spinosa* species. The sections of twigs that initiate the flower buds are the terminal ends. The most famous parts of the plant are the closed flower buds, or capers, which are eaten by people. These flower buds should not be mistaken with the immature fruits, known as caper berries, which have a harsh flavor and a greenish appearance^[16]. Typically, the fruit and flower buds are both salted, pickled, and used as ingredients, seasonings, sauces, or garnishes^[17,18].

Environmental Condition and Cultivation

Caper can grow on a variety of soil types, including alfisols, regosols, and lithosols, and is adaptable to poor soils. It is also common in rocky terrain and on mountains. It responds well to soils that are volcanic or alkaline. The pH of the soil can range from 6.1 to 8.5^[19-21]. Immediately following a rainstorm in April or May, caper plants proliferate widely before beginning to wither in September or October. It evolved defenses against high radiation and temperature, and it appears to be free of water stress or photo-inhibition symptoms^[22, 23, 24]. From West Africa to the Norfolk Islands in the Pacific, the *Capparis* subgenus *Capparis* uses caper plants practically everywhere^[25]. The majority of the species are valuable for

food or medicine. Turkey, Morocco^[20], Spain, Greece, France, and Italy (particularly Sicily and the Aeolian islands of Salina and Pantelleria in the Mediterranean)^[26] are notable suppliers. Around 10,000 tonnes are thought to be produced on average each year: 3500-4500 tonnes in Turkey, 3000 tonnes in Morocco, 500-1000 tonnes in Spain, and 1000-2000 tonnes in other nations^[19].

In the spring, treated seeds are planted in sandy soil covered by glass, and the plants are subsequently moved outside when the weather is warm and stable. Capers can also be grown from cuttings of short branches that are framed in a glasshouse and planted in a sandy soil^[27]. Additionally, some growers (like as those in Italy) choose cultivars, particularly the spineless (high harvesting) varieties, in order to create a high-quality product. Additionally, they shorten the time between harvests to ensure the collection of little buds, and they employ some strategic marketing to raise the value of the product (quality labeling, product traceability, etc.)^[28].

Phytochemistry

C. spinosa is unquestionably one of the medicinal plants that have been investigated the most in terms of its phytochemical components. Alkaloids, flavonoids, glucosinolates, phenolic acids, terpenoids, and other chemicals are present in the chemical makeup of the various components. A quick synopsis of the major chemical classes of the discovered chemicals is provided to help readers comprehend the plant's genuine therapeutic potential even if this review does not aim to be an exhaustive review of the chemistry.

Alkaloids

A wide collection of secondary natural metabolites known as alkaloids are those that have one or more nitrogen atoms in their structure. The new tetrahydroquinoline acid (1) from the stems and fruits of the plant is one of the numerous alkaloids discovered from *C. spinosa* thus far [29]. Since it has a carbon skeleton that bears both amino and carboxylic acid groups, this substance can actually be thought of as a new amino acid. (2) has been obtained from fruits and is another modified amino acid or alkaloid [30].

Flavonoids

One of the most varied polyphenolic natural compounds; flavonoids are made up of two aromatic 6-membered rings connected by a 3-carbon chain, giving them a 15-carbon skeleton. The C6 aromatic ring and C3-side chains are produced biochemically using the shikimic acid pathway, whereas the other aromatic ring is produced using the acetate process. Flavonoids can be divided into a number of sub-classes according to the degree to which the linking chain is cyclized to produce the third ring, the location of the aromatic ring's attachment to the side chain, and the chemical makeup of the linking chain, including the presence or absence of double bonds and the pattern of oxidation, among other factors. These include neoflavonoids, isoflavonoids, chalcones, flavones, flavonols, and flavanones. Given that they have a variety of pharmacological actions, from antidiabetic [31, 32].

Chemical constituents

Although 145 different compounds were found in the volatile oils of *C. spinosa*, aldehydes (22%), esters (21%), and compounds containing sulfur (8.42%) were the main components. Additionally confirmed

were the presence of sesquiterpenes, monoterpenes, and capric acid [33]. By using fractionation, total phenols and glucosinolates were extracted, and it was discovered that neither class of chemical compounds interfered with the other's activity. The mature fruits of *C. spinosa* were used to isolate new (6S)-hydroxy-3-oxo-ionol glucosides, corchoinoside C (6S, 9S)-roseoside, and prenyl glucosides [34]. Cappariloside A, stachydrine, an adenosine nucleoside, hypoxanthine, -sitosterol, vanillic acid, p-hydroxybenzoic acid, protocatechuric acid, daucosterol, uracil, butanedioc acid, and uridine were also present in the fruits of *C. spinosa* [34].

Caper Berries Use in Treatment of Diseases

Type 2 Diabetic

In most countries, diabetes mellitus type 2 is one of the diseases with the highest prevalence and fastest rate of growth [35]. Several studies have demonstrated that, in addition to standard anti-diabetic medication, nutrition, herbal remedies, and complementary and alternative medicine therapies have positive effects and improve glucose homeostasis in diabetic patients [36, 37]. The caper, *Cap-parisspinosa* L., is a member of the Capparidaceae family and likely evolved in arid parts of central or western Asia [38]. Due to the perception that caper fruits and flower buds have hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic effects, diabetic patients use them as food [39-41]. Iranian diabetic patients take the pickled caper fruit at a dose of 2–8 g daily as a cure. Despite certain ethnobotanical surveys suggesting caper use in anti-diabetic compounds, folk medicine [39-41].

Antioxidant Activity

The antioxidant benefits of various caper sections, which may be beneficial in preventing several degenerative disorders, were studied. Antioxidant activity of an aqueous infusion made from Croatian caper flower tips was assessed both before and after *in vitro* digestion [42]. Before digestion, there was significant and dose-dependent antioxidant activity as determined by the 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) method, α -carotene bleaching method, and copper-induced oxidation of human low-density lipoprotein (LDL). Bioactive components such as rutin, kaempferol 3-O-rutinoside, isorhamnetin 3-O-rutinoside, and derivatives of cinnamoylquinic acid may be responsible for this action. However, the majority of phenolic compounds degrade following *in vitro* digestion. The infusion's antioxidant activity consequently drastically declines. It's interesting to note that the type of initial matrix influences the loss of phenolic chemicals, with caper infusion being less susceptible to degradation [42].

Anticarcinogenic Activity

Methyl isothiocyanate, a byproduct of glucocapparin breakdown, predominated in the composition of the essential oil, whereas flavonoids in the water infusion were a good source of antiproliferative actions against colon cancer cells. Both the essential oil and the aqueous infusion inhibit the proliferation of HT-29 cells in a time- and dose-dependent manner, with the essential oil having slightly lower efficacy than the aqueous infusion (44.3% of inhibition after 72 h vs. 54.4%, respectively). Additionally, the effects on the activation of nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B) were investigated. The effects of essential oil

and aqueous infusion on NF- κ B activity were dose-dependent, with the latter once more having a stronger effect than the former (54.8% of inhibition vs. 19.0%, respectively). Finally, a dose-dependent G2/M arrest is brought about by caper essential oil and aqueous infusion [43].

Immunostimulant and Antitumoral Activity

By up-regulating the expression of unusual pro-inflammatory cytokines, methanolic extract of *C. spinosa* buds may help improve immune surveillance of human peripheral blood mononuclear cells against virus infection. It suppressed the replication of herpes simplex virus type 2 and increased the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines like interleukin-12, interferon, and tumor necrosis factor [44]. Additionally, *C. sikkimensis* roots were used to identify an inhibitor of *in vitro* tumor cell multiplication [45]. More recently, a protein with strong anti-proliferative effects on tumor cells and HIV-1 inhibitory effects was discovered. From *C. spinosa* seeds, transcriptase and modest antifungal activity have been extracted [46]. These significant biological activities were most likely caused by the significant amount of antioxidants, which have high anti-disease activity. In fact, it has been noted that certain carotenoids can prevent chemically induced carcinogenesis in the buccal pouch of hamsters [47]. Tocopherols are crucial in the prevention of cancer [48]. Phenolic substances have anti-tumor properties [49]. Some aldehydes that function as a replication inhibitor for tumor cells *in vitro* may also be responsible for the biological actions outlined above [45].

Traditional Uses

The fruits and flower buds of capers, which are typically salted and pickled, are rich in nutrients and serve as significant food supplements for humans. Caper fruits, for instance, provide 9 mg of iron, 65 mg of phosphorus, 67 mg of calcium, and 24.5 g of protein per 100 g, in addition to 3 mg of dietary fiber, 5 mg of carbs, 0.9 mg of fat, and 4 mg of vitamin C. Fruit extracts and caper buds can both be utilized as taste enhancers [50].

For a very long time, *C. spinosa* L. has been used in traditional phytomedicine to treat a wide range of illnesses [51]. In ancient Egypt and Arab societies, the roots were used to heal liver and renal ailments [52]. To treat paralysis, ancient Romans utilized the buds of *C. spinosa* L. [53]. Different preparations from the root powder have been used traditionally to treat osteoarthritis and rheumatic joint inflammation in numerous countries in the Mediterranean basin [54]. Caperbuds are still used to treat eye infections in some parts of Morocco, and the dried fruits can be eaten internally with a glass of water to lower blood pressure and manage diabetic complications [55, 56].

Different *C. spinosa* components have been widely utilized in traditional medicine to treat a variety of human ailments [57, 58, 59]. According to reports, rheumatism, digestive issues, headaches, renal and liver disease, as well as toothaches, have all been treated using the aerial portions and roots of *C. spinosa* [60, 58, 61, 62, 63]. Arabian traditional medicine has proposed using the leaf, roots, and buds of *C. spinosa* to cure a variety of human illnesses, including spleen disorders, stomach issues, skin disorders, earaches, renal disorders, and hepatic disorders [64, 65, 66]. It has also been

suggested for the treatment of convulsions, paralysis, and gum issues [67, 68, 66]. Its fruits have historically been used to cure rheumatism, diabetes, headaches, and fever [67, 68, 66]. The roots, fruit, and bark of *C. spinosa* have also reportedly been employed in Iranian traditional medicine as diuretics, tonics, and antimalarials [69, 70, 71]. Additionally, *C. spinosa* leaves have been utilised for centuries as analgesics, hemorrhagic, rheumatic, and anti-inflammatory drugs [66]. Additionally, *C. spinosa* is said to have positive effects on coughs and asthma [68]. Additionally, *C. spinosa* flowers have been touted as erection-inducing stimulants [68].

Conclusion

One of the most significant and widely available edible plants is *C. spinosa*. Numerous pieces of scientific evidence indicate that *C. spinosa* has a variety of pharmacological effects. The objective of this paper was to review the material that is currently accessible on the pharmacological effects of this species. In conclusion, although if many of them exist in low amounts, especially after fermentation, the positive benefits of *C. spinosa* are due to the high number of bioactive natural products, especially polyphenolic compounds. Furthermore, there are no scientific studies on the negative effects of its intake.

As a huge spontaneous plant, the *Capparis* species has a variety of uses in traditional medicine. The pharmacology and chemistry of this plant have recently undergone substantial research. Numerous advantageous substances have been found in the various *Capparis* sections, both fermented and non-fermented, according to chemical analyses.

The ancient applications are supported by biological investigations that have found strong anti-Type 2 diabetes, antioxidative, anticarcinogenic, antiinflammatory, antiarthritic, immunostimulant, and antitumor

action. Nevertheless, clinical testing is required to confirm the use of this species in medical practise, despite the significant and varied pharmacological investigations that are now accessible.

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